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**Direct measurements of luminal Ca²⁺ with endo-lysosomal GFP-aequorin
reveal functional IP₃ receptors**

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Article: Direct measurements of luminal Ca²⁺ with endo-lysosomal GFP-aequorin reveal functional IP₃ receptors

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1 **Direct measurements of luminal Ca²⁺ with endo-lysosomal GFP-aequorin**
2 **reveal functional IP₃ receptors**

3

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35 **KEYWORDS:**

36 Endo-lysosome, Ca²⁺, Ca²⁺ signalling, aequorin, genetically encoded Ca²⁺
37 indicator, acidic organelle, IP₃R, Ca²⁺ release.

38 **eTOC SUMMARY**

39 Calvo et al. describe a new bioluminescent sensor for measuring luminal Ca²⁺ in a
40 mildly acidic subcompartment of the endo-lysosomal system. This Ca²⁺ store
41 accumulates high Ca²⁺ content via active uptake and releases it via endogenous
42 IP₃ receptors with responses comparable to those activated by TPCs and
43 TRPMLs.

44

45 **ABSTRACT (159w)**

46 Endo-lysosomes are considered acidic Ca^{2+} stores but direct measurements of
47 luminal Ca^{2+} within them are limited. Here we report that the Ca^{2+} -sensitive
48 luminescent protein aequorin does not reconstitute with its cofactor at highly acidic
49 pH but that a significant fraction of the probe is functional within a mildly acidic
50 compartment when targeted to the endo-lysosomal system. We leveraged this
51 probe (ELGA) to report Ca^{2+} dynamics in this compartment. We show that Ca^{2+}
52 uptake is ATP-dependent and sensitive to blockers of ER Ca^{2+} pumps. We find
53 that the Ca^{2+} mobilizing messenger IP_3 evokes robust luminal responses in wild
54 type cells, but not in IP_3R knock-out cells. Responses were comparable to those
55 evoked by activation of the endo-lysosomal ion channels TPCs and TRPMLs.
56 Stimulation with IP_3 -forming agonists also mobilized the store in intact cells. Super-
57 resolution microscopy analysis was consistent with the presence of IP_3Rs within
58 the endo-lysosomal system. Our data reveal a physiologically-relevant, IP_3 -
59 sensitive store of Ca^{2+} within the endo-lysosomal system.

60 INTRODUCTION

61 The endo-lysosomal (EL) system has emerged as a relevant player in subcellular
62 Ca^{2+} signalling alongside the better characterised endoplasmic reticulum (ER)
63 (Morgan et al., 2011; Patel and Docampo, 2010; Yang et al., 2019). EL Ca^{2+} has
64 been implicated in most of the organelle's functions, such as late endosome-
65 lysosome fusion, lysosomal exocytosis, and membrane repair. Impaired Ca^{2+}
66 signalling can cause defects in EL trafficking and eventually can provoke lysosome
67 storage diseases (Platt, 2018). These so called acidic Ca^{2+} stores are thought to
68 accumulate high amounts of Ca^{2+} (in the range of 0.4-0.6 mM), similar to the ER
69 (Christensen et al., 2002; Lloyd-Evans et al., 2008). Akin to ER-localised
70 receptor/ Ca^{2+} channels for the second messenger IP_3 which mediate Ca^{2+} release
71 in response to IP_3 -forming hormones, various Ca^{2+} -permeable channels have
72 been shown to localize to membranes of the EL system. These include Mucolipin
73 transient receptor potential (TRPML) channels, two pore channels (TPCs) and
74 P_2X_4 receptors (Klingl et al., 2025; Rosato et al., 2021). TRPML1 is an ubiquitously
75 expressed channel specifically activated by phosphatidylinositol 3,5-bisphosphate
76 ($\text{PI}(3,5)\text{P}_2$), a low abundant phosphoinositide enriched in endomembranes, and
77 which is mutated in type IV mucopolidosis (Dong et al., 2010).

78 The ER accumulates Ca^{2+} via SERCA pumps. In contrast, the mechanism
79 responsible for EL Ca^{2+} uptake has not yet been fully elucidated, mainly because
80 of technical difficulties. It is assumed that the vacuolar-type ATPase (V-ATPase)
81 which is present in the EL membrane and maintains the proton gradient, drives
82 Ca^{2+} into the lysosomal lumen via a transporter similar to $\text{Ca}^{2+}/\text{H}^+$ exchangers
83 present in yeast, plants and in some animals (Melchionda et al., 2016; Mindell,
84 2012). Other routes proposed for Ca^{2+} uptake include the Parkinson's disease
85 linked ATPase, ATP13A2 (Narayanaswamy et al., 2019) and transmembrane
86 protein 165 (TMEM165) which is present in the Golgi but also to a lesser extent in
87 lysosomes, where it may import Ca^{2+} in a pH dependent manner (Chen et al.,
88 2025; Jankauskas et al., 2024; Zajac et al., 2024). This view has been challenged
89 by the proposal that the ER, not the pH gradient, through IP_3R tunnels Ca^{2+} into
90 the endo-lysosomes (Atakpa et al., 2019; Garrity et al., 2016). But these
91 conclusions were drawn from indirect monitoring of cytosolic Ca^{2+} using
92 conventional organic Ca^{2+} dyes or genetically-encoded Ca^{2+} indicators targeted to

93 the cytosolic site of the EL system (Kilpatrick et al., 2016; Shen et al., 2012)
94 thereby providing only qualitative insights into EL Ca²⁺ uptake.

95 Direct measurements of luminal Ca²⁺ within the EL system have been challenging
96 due to the acidic pH which interferes with Ca²⁺ binding and thus requires careful
97 calibration. In this study, we report the use of the Ca²⁺-sensitive luminescent
98 protein aequorin targeted to the endo-lysosome. In general, aequorin is
99 considered less sensitive to acidic pH than fluorescent genetically encoded Ca²⁺
100 indicators (Johnson and Shimomura, 1978; Shimomura et al., 1974). But
101 surprisingly, we find that aequorin does not reconstitute well at extreme acidic pH
102 and therefore reports Ca²⁺ in a mildly acidic compartment of the EL system. We
103 show that this compartment accumulates Ca²⁺ via active uptake and releases it via
104 endogenous IP₃ receptors. Our study introduces a new tool for measuring Ca²⁺
105 within the EL system and extends the actions of IP₃ to the endo-lysosomal system.

106

107 **RESULTS**

108 ***ELGA as a novel endo-lysosomal Ca²⁺ indicator***

109 We recently introduced genetically-encoded Ca²⁺ indicators based on aequorin
110 fused to GFP (Rodriguez-Garcia et al., 2014; Rodriguez-Prados et al., 2015).
111 Here, we targeted them to the EL system by fusing the N-terminal of GFP-
112 aequorin (GA) to the C-terminal of the tetanus-insensitive vesicle-associated
113 membrane protein 7 (VAMP7), a marker of the late endosomes and secretory
114 lysosomes (Pryor et al., 2004; Vats and Galli, 2022) (**Fig. 1A**). VAMP-7 is
115 composed of a cytosolic region, an EL transmembrane domain and a luminal C-
116 terminal domain. Therefore, the Ca²⁺ indicators are expected to be confined to the
117 EL lumen (**Fig. 1B**). Due to the expected high endo-lysosomal luminal Ca²⁺, we
118 introduced the D119A mutation in aequorin to lower the affinity for Ca²⁺. This
119 probe was dubbed ELGA (for Endo-Lysosomal GFP-Aequorin). We generated a
120 second variant (ELGA1) with additional substitutions (D117A, and D163A) to
121 further reduce the affinity, lowering rate of aequorin consumption and thereby
122 allowing longer recordings (up to ~1h). Note that GA1 was a variant previously
123 published as GAP1 (Rodriguez-Garcia et al., 2014; Rodriguez-Prados et al., 2015)
124 but renamed here to maintain a comprehensive nomenclature. Both probes can

125 measure Ca^{2+} in the range of 100-1000 μM (**Fig. S1A**). The Ca^{2+} sensors were
126 expressed (either transiently or stably) in mammalian cells using a relatively weak
127 herpes simplex virus type 1 (HSV-1) promoter (Geller, 1991), to limit the amount of
128 expressed protein and, hence, to minimize mistargeting.

129 As shown in **Fig. 1C and video 1**, ELGA and ELGA1 both localized to punctate
130 structures. To characterize the subcellular distribution of the ELGAs, we performed
131 colocalization analysis with various endogenous organellar markers. **Fig. 1D**
132 shows representative confocal images of HEK293T cells transfected with ELGA
133 and fixed one day later. The endogenous lysosome-associated membrane protein
134 2 (LAMP-2) was assayed by immunodetection with a specific antibody (**Fig. 1D**).
135 There was colocalization of ELGA with LAMP2, whereas there was no significant
136 overlap with markers for other organelles such as ER, early endosome, or
137 mitochondria (**Figs. 1D, S2A and B, and Table S1**). Altogether, these results
138 indicate that the majority of the ELGA indicator is localized to a subset of endo-
139 lysosomes.

140 ***ELGA reports Ca^{2+} in mildly acidic compartments***

141 To analyse the ability of aequorin to report Ca^{2+} at acidic pH, we compared the
142 maximal luminescence signal triggered by Ca^{2+} in the pH range from 4.5 up to 7.2.
143 Recombinant GA regenerated with coelenterazine showed maximal luminescence
144 activity at pH 7.2 that decreased proportionally at lower pHs (6.5 and 6.0 pH) up to
145 a threshold of 5.5 pH, below which the Ca^{2+} sensor was not functional (**Fig. 1E**
146 **and F**). Similar results were obtained with GA1 or with the original aequorin, either
147 reconstituted with native coelenterazine or with its lower affinity *n* analogue (**Figs.**
148 **S1B-D**), indicating that the effect of acidic pH on the luminescent function is
149 independent on the affinity of aequorin for Ca^{2+} . This was surprising, given
150 previous calibration/performance studies at acidic pH (Mitchell et al., 2001; Ronco
151 et al., 2015; SantoDomingo et al., 2010). If the aequorin-based Ca^{2+} sensor was
152 first reconstituted at near-neutral pH (7.2) and then, shifted to pH 4.5 for the
153 luminescence assay, the luminescence activity was recovered, suggesting that the
154 lack of light emission is due to disrupted binding of the cofactor to apoaequorin
155 (**Fig. 1G**).

156 The above findings precluded measurement of Ca^{2+} at highly acidic pH such as
157 that found in lysosomes. But because the pH of endocytic organelles is diverse
158 (e.g., early endosome, pH 6.5; late endosomes, pH 6.0; lysosome, pH 4.5), we
159 reasoned that ELGAs could be used to report Ca^{2+} in less acidic compartments
160 within the EL system. To determine whether ELGAs reside in such compartments,
161 we leveraged the pH sensitivity of the GFP moiety in ELGA. GFP fluorescence is
162 quenched at acidic pH ($\text{pK}_a \sim 6$). Thus, any detectable GFP fluorescence in live
163 cells should reflect targeting to a compartment with a $\text{pH} > 5$ within the range where
164 aequorin can be reconstituted. As shown in **Fig. 1H**, punctate GFP fluorescence
165 was readily detectable in live HeLa and HEK293 cells transfected with ELGA.

166 To assess the properties of the probes at less acidic pH, we performed Ca^{2+}
167 calibrations at pH 7.2 and 6. Essentially, similar values were obtained at both pH
168 values, indicating no major effect within this range. As shown in **Fig. 1I**, the affinity
169 of GA1 for Ca^{2+} was $\sim 350 \mu\text{M}$ at pH 7.2.

170 Taken together, these results identify ELGAs as reporters of Ca^{2+} within mildly
171 acidic compartments.

172 ***Uptake of Ca^{2+} is ATP-dependent and sensitive to blockers of SERCA***

173 In order to directly monitor uptake and release of Ca^{2+} within the EL compartment,
174 we used digitonin-permeabilized HEK293T cells expressing ELGA1 perfused with
175 a cytosol-like solution. As we expected the EL system to be a high Ca^{2+} content
176 store, it needed to be depleted of Ca^{2+} before aequorin was regenerated with its
177 cofactor to avoid its premature consumption. But the mechanisms of store filling
178 are unclear. We first tested Bafilomycin A1 prior to adding the coelenterazine: this
179 compound inhibits the V-type ATPase and has been used widely to disrupt the
180 activity of putative Ca^{2+} - H^+ exchangers. Bafilomycin A1 treatment did not produce
181 a measurable luminescent signal (**Fig. S3A**), indicating that aequorin had been
182 consumed likely because the target store was not emptied of Ca^{2+} . These data are
183 consistent with functional targeting of ELGA to a non-highly acidic compartment.

184 By contrast, incubation with the reversible SERCA inhibitor tert-butylhydroquinone
185 (tBHQ), produced a robust luminescence signal with a good signal to noise ratio
186 (**Fig. 2A**). Under these conditions, perfusion with cytosol-like medium (free $[\text{Ca}^{2+}]$
187 = 200 nM) initiated Ca^{2+} uptake at a rate of $8 \pm 0.6 \mu\text{M/s}$ ($n=36$), reaching a value

188 of $[Ca^{2+}]_{EL}$ at the steady-state of $365 \pm 21 \mu M$ ($n=54$) in 3 ± 0.6 min ($n=7$) (**Fig. 2A**
189 **and B**). Other cell types tested, e.g. HeLa, CHO, MDCK or cortical astrocytes
190 displayed similar responses (**Figs. 2B and S3B**). We tested the effect of
191 Bafilomycin A1. Bafilomycin A1 ($1 \mu M$) added acutely or following incubation for 1
192 h had little effect on the $[Ca^{2+}]_{EL}$ (**Figs. S4A and B**), consistent with the failure to
193 reconstitute the probe in its presence.

194 Ca^{2+} uptake was ATP-dependent because there was little change in luminescence
195 in the absence of ATP ($90 \pm 4\%$ inhibition, $n=7$; **Figs. 2C and F, and S1E and F**).
196 Similarly, the SERCA inhibitors thapsigargin or tBHQ provoked a complete
197 inhibition of the EL Ca^{2+} uptake ($98 \pm 1\%$, $n=7$; and $97 \pm 2\%$, $n=8$; **Figs. 2D and E**,
198 respectively). Washing out of tBHQ rapidly restored the Ca^{2+} uptake up to normal
199 rate (**Fig. 2E**). Once the endo-lysosomal lumen was fully replenished with Ca^{2+} ,
200 reducing cytosolic Ca^{2+} (by addition of 0.1 mM EGTA) caused a progressive and
201 complete decline in the $[Ca^{2+}]_{EL}$ at a rate of $\sim 2.0 \mu M/s$ (**Fig. 2G**). Likewise, removal
202 of ATP or application of tBHQ, either in the presence or absence of Ca^{2+} , emptied
203 the EL- Ca^{2+} store. Statistical quantifications of the EL- Ca^{2+} -uptake and Ca^{2+} -exit
204 rate are shown in **Figs. 2F and H**, respectively. Replacement of the EGTA buffer
205 used to clamp the $[Ca^{2+}]_C$ with the faster chelator BAPTA did not have any
206 significant effect on the endo-lysosomal Ca^{2+} levels at the steady-state (**Fig. 2I**
207 **and S6B**). In addition, no significant differences were observed in the rate of tBHQ
208 induced EL- Ca^{2+} passive exit between permeabilized and intact cells (**Fig. 2J**).

209 Collectively, these results indicate that the endo-lysosome can accumulate high
210 amounts of Ca^{2+} through a SERCA mechanism.

211 ***IP₃ mobilizes Ca²⁺ from endo-lysosomal Ca²⁺ stores***

212 Addition of IP_3 ($2 \mu M$, 30s) reliably produced a fast and strong Ca^{2+} release from
213 the endo-lysosomal store that reduced the endo-lysosomal luminal $[Ca^{2+}]_{EL}$ by 72
214 $\pm 1\%$ ($n= 18$) (**Figs. 3A and 3F**). The IP_3 -evoked Ca^{2+} release was very robust and
215 consistent in all cell types tested (HeLa, CHO or MDCK cells; representative
216 results are shown in **Figs. S3C**). This effect was concentration dependent, from
217 $0.01 \mu M$, that produced a small but detectable effect, up to $10 \mu M$, a maximal
218 effect, comparable to that with $30 \mu M$, the highest IP_3 concentration tested (**Fig.**
219 **3B**, and summary data in **Fig. 3C**).

220 To test specificity of the IP₃ response, we used IP₃R-null HEK293 (HEK-3KO) cell
221 line generated by CRISPR/Cas9 technology lacking all three IP₃ receptor subtypes
222 (Alzayady et al., 2016). As shown in **Fig. 3D and F**, IP₃-induced Ca²⁺ release was
223 abrogated (1.36 ± 0.97 % (n= 12). Interestingly, in these cells both the EL-Ca²⁺
224 refilling rate (6.7 ± 0.7 μM/s) and the [Ca²⁺]_{EL} reached at the steady-state ($369 \pm$
225 32 μM; n= 12) coincided with those values obtained in IP₃ receptor replete control
226 cells (8.0 ± 0.6 μM/s; n= 36 and 365 ± 21 μM; n= 53) (**Fig. S5A and B**). This
227 suggests that, unless there are compensatory effects, IP₃R is not essential for
228 refilling the EL Ca²⁺ store. We also examined the effect of IP₃ in HEK-3KO cells
229 upon re-expression of IP₃R1. As shown in **Figs. 3E and F**, the IP₃ response was
230 partially rescued (54 ± 1 %; n= 7). In an independent approach, we used heparin,
231 an inhibitor of the IP₃R. Heparin completely blocked the IP₃ response (92 ± 2 %
232 inhibition; n= 5; **Figs. 3G and H**). By contrast, BAPTA did not have any effect on
233 the IP₃-induced Ca²⁺ release from the EL (**Figs. S6A-C**). Collectively, both genetic
234 and pharmacological approaches reveal the presence of functional IP₃R within
235 the EL Ca²⁺ store that support robust luminal Ca²⁺ responses.

236 ***ELGA responses are independent of the ER***

237 Because of the similarities in the properties of the Ca²⁺ stores reported by ELGA
238 and the ER with respect to both Ca²⁺ uptake and Ca²⁺ release by IP₃, we
239 considered the possibility that a fraction of the probe may be mistargeted to the
240 ER.

241 We first explored the Ca²⁺ release pathway triggered by NAADP, which specifically
242 activates endo-lysosomal TPCs. NAADP evoked a fast reversible response that
243 released EL-Ca²⁺, both in HEK293T (**Fig. 4A**) and HeLa (**Fig. 4B**) cells. The
244 responses were, however, inconsistent and observable in around ~50% of trials in
245 both cell types (**Figs. 4C and D**). In those experiments that showed a response,
246 this accounted for 30% of the luminal Ca²⁺. The NAADP response was reversible
247 upon washing out and sequential additions of NAADP provoked Ca²⁺ release of
248 similar amplitude (**Fig. 4A**) but smaller than those stimulated by IP₃, added to the
249 same cells for comparison. Cells unresponsive to NAADP still responded robustly
250 to IP₃ (**Fig. 4C**). Incubation for 3h with Bafilomycin A1 (1μM) did not produce any
251 effect on the responses to NAADP or to IP₃ (**Fig. S4C and D**), consistent with our

252 previous results where treatment with Bafilomycin A1 did not provoke an emptying
253 of Ca²⁺ in the target store (**Figs. S4A and B**).

254 We next examined the Ca²⁺ release pathway activated by TRPMLs. We first
255 expressed TRPML1-Cherry and analysed its colocalization with ELGA by confocal
256 microscopy in fixed HEK293T cells. As shown in **Fig. 4E**, both probes were
257 targeted to the same compartment. Colocalization significantly decreased in live
258 cells (**Figs. 4E and F**) indicating that a proportion of ELGA is located to acidic,
259 non-fluorescent vesicles in live cells that become fluorescent when the pH
260 increases upon fixation. We also used super-resolution microscopy to more
261 accurately localise ELGA (**Figs. S2B and C, and Table S2**). ELGA was resolved
262 as clear puncta and colocalised with TRPML1 in single EL vesicles (**Fig. S2C**),
263 consistent with our confocal analyses. We expected the GFP moiety of ELGA to
264 be on the luminal surface of the EL vesicle (**Fig. 1B**). To facilitate visualization of
265 ELGA, we performed experiments using vacuolin to enlarge vesicles (**Fig. S2D**)
266 but it was difficult to resolve the luminal and cytosolic surfaces.

267 There was no co-localization of TRPML1, fused to GFP, with an ER marker (**Fig.**
268 **S7A**). We confirmed this result by electron microscopy in HEK cells expressing
269 TRPML1-Cherry stained with antibodies against Cherry (in single labelling) and,
270 Cherry and KDEL, as an endogenous ER marker (in double labelling experiments;
271 **Figs. 4G, S7B and C**). In single labelling, TRPML accumulated in endosomes but
272 not the ER. In double labelling, there was a clear segregation, with no overlap.
273 Collectively, these results provide further evidence that expression of TRPML1 is
274 restricted to the EL system.

275 In transiently expressing TRPML1 HEK293T cells, ML-SA1 (20 μM, 30s) produced
276 a robust EL-Ca²⁺ release of 38 ± 4% (n= 15) of the total EL luminal Ca²⁺ content
277 (**Figs. 4H and I**). Upon application, ML-SA1 exhibited a lag time of ~20s and it
278 continued releasing Ca²⁺ once the agonist was washed out. Consecutive
279 applications of ML-SA1 evoked responses of similar amplitude, indicating no
280 desensitization of the channel. The time to refill the store after the washing out
281 was ~5 min. Full concentration-effect relationship for the Ca²⁺ release response
282 showed an EC₅₀ value of 7 ± 1 μM (**Figs. 4I and J**). Comparable responses were
283 observed in TRPML1-expressing HeLa cells (**Figs. S5C-F**). In accord, the

284 response to ML-SA1 was blocked by the specific TRPML-antagonists ML-SI1
285 (**Figs. 4K and S5D**) and ML-SI3 (**Fig. S5E**) but not by heparin (**Fig. S5F**) or in an
286 IP₃R3KO cell line (**Figs. S5G-I**). We also activated TRPML1 with its endogenous
287 activator PI(3,5)P₂. As shown in **Fig. 4L**, PI(3,5)P₂ evoked EL-Ca²⁺ release in cells
288 expressing TRPML1 albeit modestly compared to ML-SA1. Statistical
289 quantification is summarized in **Fig. 4M**. The EL-Ca²⁺ release provoked by
290 PI(3,5)P₂ was concentration-dependent (**Figs. 4N and O**). We also expressed
291 TRPML3 in HEK293T cells and activated the channel with the synthetic agonist
292 EVP-21 (Grimm et al., 2010; Kim et al., 2022). As shown in **Fig. 4P**, cells
293 expressing TRPML3 responded to EVP-21 with a robust Ca²⁺ release, whereas
294 those expressing TRPML1 did not (**Figs. S6E-G**).

295 Interestingly, TRPML1 expression drastically reduced steady state levels of Ca²⁺
296 reported by ELGA1 (**Fig. 4Q**). In contrast, Ca²⁺ levels in the ER measured using
297 the same reporter targeted to the ER were unchanged upon TRPML1 expression,
298 indicating that the channel is specifically leaky in the EL store. These functional
299 data distinguish EL and ER Ca²⁺ stores. In accord, there was no correlation
300 between EL and ER Ca²⁺ levels reported by the corresponding GA1 in the cell
301 types used (**Fig. 4R**). Activation of TRPML1 also mobilized Ca²⁺ from the ER,
302 although to a lesser extent than in the EL system (**Figs. 4S and V**). TRPML1-
303 mediated ER release tended to be reduced by BAPTA, although the responses
304 were inconsistent (**Figs. 4T and V**). In contrast, BAPTA treatment significantly
305 increased the ML-SA1 signal in the EL (**Figs. 4U and V**). These results further
306 distinguish EL and ER Ca²⁺ stores.

307 Altogether, these data show that ELGA accurately reports the properties of *bona*
308 *fade* EL Ca²⁺ channels.

309 **High resolution subcellular localisation analysis of IP₃ receptors**

310 We applied several high resolution microscopy techniques to assess whether IP₃
311 receptors localized to the EL system. We used HeLa cells in which endogenous
312 IP₃R1 is tagged with EGFP by gene editing (Thillaiappan et al., 2017). Results
313 from stimulated emission depletion (STED) super-resolution microscopy showed
314 that IP₃R1-EGFP displayed a well resolved punctate distribution in fixed cells (**Fig.**
315 **5A**). This distribution was compared to expressed EL channels. We detected a
316 number of IP₃R1 puncta that colocalized with TRPML1 (**Figs. 5Aa-b**). Essentially,

317 similar results were obtained with TPC1 (**Figs. 5Ac-d**). In addition, we found
318 partial colocalization of IP₃R1 (**Figs. 5Ae-f**) or SERCA2 (**Fig. S8A**) with
319 endogenous LAMP2 although overlap was modest. In another cell type, HEK293,
320 using a specific antibody against endogenous IP₃R3 we localized IP₃R3 using
321 STED microscopy. We also found evidence for partial colocalization of IP₃R3 with
322 endogenous LAMP1 (**Fig. 5B**).

323 To seek evidence for IP₃R localization with EL system in live cells, we loaded
324 IP₃R1-GFP HeLa cells with fluorescent acidotropes (LysoView650 and LysoTracker
325 red). Some IP₃R1 clearly formed puncta with endo-lysosomes using either super-
326 resolution microscopy (STED; **Fig. 5C**) or total internal reflection fluorescence
327 microscopy (TIRFM; **Fig. 5D**).

328 Finally, we examined to what extent ELGA colocalizes with endogenous IP₃Rs.
329 Since ELGA and EGFP-IP₃R1 in HeLa cells are both GFP fusions, we generated a
330 new red version of ELGA replacing the GFP domain with Scarlet fluorescent
331 protein and dubbed it ELSA (Endo-Lysosome Scarlet-Aequorin). We chose this
332 fluorophore due to its advantageous properties in the red channel for super-
333 resolution microscopy (**Fig. S8B**). This indicator is also functional in luminescence
334 assays (**Fig. S8C**). As shown in **Fig. 5E** we could confirm partial colocalization
335 between IP₃R and ELSA consistent with the degree of overlap between IP₃R and
336 EL markers.

337 In sum, these data support the view that a subpopulation of IP₃Rs are physically
338 localized to the endo-lysosomal system.

339 ***Physiological IP₃-forming stimuli mobilize Ca²⁺ from endo-lysosomal Ca²⁺*** 340 ***stores***

341 To further characterize endo-lysosomal Ca²⁺ dynamics, we assessed luminal Ca²⁺
342 levels in intact cells. Addition of 1 mM CaCl₂ refilled the EL Ca²⁺store up to a
343 steady-state of 234 ± 29 μM (n= 12) (**Fig. 6A**).

344 To probe the functionality of IP₃ receptors, we stimulated live cells with ATP which
345 activates endogenous P2Y receptors or carbachol which activates muscarinic
346 receptors. ATP and carbachol provoked fast and reversible EL Ca²⁺responses of
347 35.81 ± 2.34 % (n= 7) and 19.88 ± 1.87 % (n= 5), respectively (**Fig. 6A**). ML-SA1
348 also produced reproducible responses in cells expressing TRPML1 although it was

349 ineffective in wild type cells (**Figs. 6A and B**). Similar experiments were performed
350 in polarised MDCK cells (**Fig. 6C**). This cell type displayed a comparable steady-
351 state EL-Ca²⁺ that was almost completely discharged upon cell activation with ATP
352 (73.72 ± 16.85 %; n= 4).

353 Finally, we examined EL responses in a primary cell type. In mouse cortical
354 astrocytes (**Fig. 6D**), ML-SA1 application elicited a negligible effect whereas a
355 subsequent pulse of ATP almost completely discharged the EL-Ca²⁺ store (87.68 ±
356 5.90 %; n= 6). A summary of the data is shown in **Fig. 6E**.

357 In sum, these data identify a widespread physiologically-relevant IP₃-sensitive
358 Ca²⁺ store within the EL system.

359 **DISCUSSION**

360 Using a new genetically-encoded Ca^{2+} indicator based on aequorin, we
361 demonstrate here the existence of a *bona-fide* endo-lysosomal Ca^{2+} store, able to
362 accumulate a high $[\text{Ca}^{2+}]$ and to release it upon physiological activation (**Fig. 6F**).

363 Our results are best explained if this endo-lysosome accumulates Ca^{2+} via an
364 active transport system such as the SERCA pump. The mechanisms by which the
365 EL accumulates Ca^{2+} are not fully elucidated. The traditional view is that the
366 lysosomal H^+ gradient is required for Ca^{2+} storage and maintenance, and that
367 dissipation of the gradient across the lysosomal membrane releases lysosomal
368 Ca^{2+} (Melchionda et al., 2016; Mindell, 2012). In humans, TMEM165 is a
369 candidate for importing Ca^{2+} into the lysosomal lumen in a pH-dependent manner
370 (Chen et al., 2025; Zajac et al., 2024). By contrast, other reports found that
371 dissipation of the proton gradient by V-ATPase inhibitors had little effect on naive
372 Ca^{2+} stores or their refilling (Garrity et al., 2016). Here, lysosomal Ca^{2+} import may
373 involve ATP13A2, which like SERCA is a P-type ATPase (Narayanaswamy et al.,
374 2019; Ramonet et al., 2012). ATP13A2 mutations are found in patients with
375 Parkinson's disease or lysosomal storage disorders (Usenovic et al., 2012; van
376 Veen et al., 2014) and evidence continues to accrue implicating lysosomal Ca^{2+}
377 defects in those diseases (Gregori et al., 2025; Hockey et al., 2015).

378 The luminal Ca^{2+} concentration is significantly lower in the EL compartment (~200-
379 400 μM) than the ER (~400-500 μM) and varies in its sensitivity to the expression
380 of TRPML1, which selectively lowers the EL Ca^{2+} store content. The EL Ca^{2+}
381 values are in agreement with previous reports (Narayanaswamy et al., 2019;
382 Ronco et al., 2015) but contrast with others (Albrecht et al., 2015). The SERCA
383 might be located at the EL membrane where it directly pumps Ca^{2+} into its lumen.

384 We show that activation of TRPML1 with MLSA1/PI(3,5)P₂, TRPML3 with EVP21
385 and TPCs with NAADP produces luminal responses, although the latter were not
386 entirely consistent. Recent studies have shown that NAADP binds to soluble
387 binding proteins to activate TPCs (Gunaratne et al., 2023; Saito et al., 2023). It is
388 possible that loss of these proteins upon permeabilization may account for NAADP
389 insensitivity. Surprisingly, IP₃ consistently produced robust Ca^{2+} release responses
390 comparable to those evoked by *bona fide* EL channels. In accord with these

391 functional data, our results with super resolution microscopy and TIRFM provide
392 direct evidence for the presence of IP₃R on the endo-lysosome vesicles. It will be
393 interesting to identify the major IP₃R isoform that is preferentially expressed in the
394 EL system. The finding that IP₃R1 could partially rescue the IP₃ signal in knock-out
395 cells supports the notion that this isoform is the major contributor and that the
396 isoforms IP₃R2/3 are responsible for fine-tuning EL-Ca²⁺ release.

397 Importantly, proteomic analysis of endo-lysosomal vesicles isolated from HEK293
398 cells by multiple different protocols, has also identified SERCA and two isoforms of
399 IP₃R in this organelle (Singh et al., 2020). Moreover, IP₃R_s are detected in endo-
400 lysosomes of numerous additional cell lines, both of mouse and human origin
401 (Akter et al., 2023). We have confirmed the presence of IP₃R_s and SERCA in
402 endo-lysosomes using LysolIP (McVeigh B.M. et al., 2025 (in press)) consistent
403 with our high resolution microscopy analysis but electron microscopy analysis of
404 IP₃ receptors is needed to strengthen this notion. Functional IP₃ receptors have
405 been documented in other acidic organelles such as secretory granules in
406 professional secretory cell types (Gerasimenko et al., 2006; Santodomingo et al.,
407 2008) and the acidocalcisome in Trypanosomes (Huang et al., 2013). But we are
408 not aware of their presence within the EL system, which extends IP₃ action to
409 potentially all cells. In this context, the compartment we describe here could be
410 considered a 'hybrid' ER-EL compartment.

411 Previous work suggested that IP₃ fills the EL system with Ca²⁺ (Atakpa et al.,
412 2018; Garrity et al., 2016) as opposed to emptying it as reported here. But direct
413 measurements of luminal Ca²⁺ in response to IP₃ were not reported previously.
414 Instead, these conclusions were based almost exclusively on indirect
415 measurements of Ca²⁺ in the cytosol. In our experiments, the lack of effect of the
416 fast chelator BAPTA on EL Ca²⁺ uptake and on release by IP₃ indicates that the
417 EL responses are likely direct, and not secondary to the ER.

418 Because reconstitution of ELGA is pH sensitive, it reports Ca²⁺ in only a sub-
419 compartment of the EL system. The EL system is very heterogeneous in
420 morphology, composition, and function. Although this organelle is globally
421 considered acidic, its luminal pH varies from 4.5 up to 6.5 in different vesicles. The
422 acidity of the vesicles has been correlated with subcellular location (Bright et al.,

423 2016; Johnson et al., 2016) likely indicative of functional diversity. Thus, Ca²⁺
424 handling, might also show heterogeneity among the various endo-lysosomal
425 vesicles not least because of the relationship between luminal Ca²⁺ and pH
426 (Christensen et al., 2002). Probes that allow spatial mapping of Ca²⁺ are required
427 to pinpoint the presence of endosomal IP₃ receptors that might release Ca²⁺ and
428 ER IP₃ receptors that might drive Ca²⁺ uptake.

429 Our intact cell studies provide evidence that IP₃-sensitive stores can be tapped
430 during physiological stimulation with IP₃-forming stimuli. The fast exit of Ca²⁺ from
431 the EL into the cytosol through IP₃Rs would generate local cytosolic Ca²⁺ signals.
432 These, in turn, could be amplified either via Ca²⁺-induced Ca²⁺ release (CICR)
433 through IP₃Rs (or RyRs in other cell types) present in the ER membrane to
434 generate global signals. Indeed, IP₃Rs have been shown to be preferentially
435 associated with lysosomes at contact sites (Atakpa et al., 2019). Such coupling
436 would be analogous to that triggering of Ca²⁺ signals by TRPML (Kilpatrick et al.,
437 2016) or TPCs (Xu and Ren, 2015; Yuan et al., 2024; Zhu et al., 2010). Our results
438 are in line with the '*chatter*' between the two organelles (Patel et al., 2010) and the
439 essential role of the ER in the EL signal in various cell types (Garrity et al., 2016;
440 López-Sanjurjo et al., 2013; Morgan et al., 2013; Yang et al., 2019). Alternatively,
441 local IP₃R-dependent Ca²⁺ signals may regulate endo-lysosomal function at basal
442 (unstimulated) levels of IP₃, again in analogy with TPCs and TRPML, which are
443 well established in regulating membrane traffic (Pryor et al., 2000; Ruas et al.,
444 2010; Vassileva et al., 2020).

445 In conclusion, our direct luminal Ca²⁺ measurements help to fill the gaps in our
446 knowledge on the Ca²⁺ signalling toolkit of the endo-lysosome system and provide
447 new insight into the dynamics of these small acidic Ca²⁺ stores and their functional
448 relationship with the ER Ca²⁺ stores.

449 **FIGURE LEGENDS**

450 **Figure 1. Design, characterization and calibration of endo-lysosomal Ca²⁺**
451 **indicators. (A)** Domain structure and mutations of the endo-lysosomal indicators
452 drawn approximately at scale. VAMP7, vesicle-associated membrane protein 7;
453 AEQ, aequorin; ELGA, endo-lysosomal GFP-Aequorin; ELGA1, endo-lysosomal
454 GAP1. **(B)** Predicted topology of ELGA and ELGA1 Ca²⁺ probes within the endo-
455 lysosome. **(C)** Representative confocal fluorescent images of equatorial plane of
456 fixed MDCK cells transiently transfected with ELGA or ELGA1. Scale bar for both
457 images, 10 μm. **(D) Upper row:** ELGA expressing HEK293T cells (*Left*, green)
458 were immunostained with a specific anti-LAMP2 antibody (*Center*, magenta).
459 Green and magenta images are merged (*Right*, *merge*). **Lower row:**
460 Colocalization of ELGA expressing HEK293T cells with the following organellar
461 markers (magenta): ER, er-Ruby-GCaMP210; early endosome, immunostained
462 with anti-early endosome antigen 1 (EE) antibody; mitochondria (mt),
463 immunostained with anti-TOM20 antibody. er-Ruby-GCaMP210 (Farrell et al.,
464 2024) colocalizes well with endogenous calreticulin (**Fig. S2A**). Scale bar for all
465 images, 5 μm. **(E)** Effect of acidic pH on GA luminescence emission. *E.coli*
466 recombinant GA apoprotein was reconstituted with native (*left*) or *n* (*right*)
467 coelenterazine (CTZ) for 20 min at the indicated pH and, then subjected to
468 luminescence emission assay triggered with 10 mM CaCl₂ (arrow) and measured
469 at the same pH. Buffers used were: acetate for range 4.5-5.5 pH; Na-MOPS for 6
470 and 6.5 pH; and Na-Hepes for 7.2 pH. Each trace is the value normalized with
471 respect to its background emission before addition of Ca²⁺. Each trace is the
472 average of 3-4 independent experiments. **(F)** Summary of peak counts values
473 (mean ± S.E.M; n=3) at various pH obtained in E. **(G)** Luminescence activity of
474 GA1 after regeneration with *n* coelenterazine at 7.2 or 4.5 pH. Peak value (mean ±
475 S.E.M; n=3) obtained from an experiment similar to (E) performed at pHs 7.2 (*blue*
476 *bar*) and 4.5 (*black bar*) or reconstituted with coelenterazine at pH 7.2 and
477 switched to pH 4.5 to measure luminescence (*pink bar*). **(H)** Expression of ELGA
478 in live HeLa and HEK293T cells. Scale bar, 10 μm. **(I)** Ca²⁺ titration curves of GA1
479 at pH 6.0 and 7.2. Each value is the mean ± S.E.M of 3-6 measurements obtained
480 from two independent protein preparations.

481 **Figure 2. The endo-lysosomal Ca^{2+} store accumulates Ca^{2+} via SERCA. (A)**
482 Representative EL- Ca^{2+} signals recorded in HEK293T cells transiently transfected
483 with ELGA1. After Ca^{2+} depletion prior to reconstitution with coelenterazine n , cells
484 were permeabilized in Ca^{2+} -free intracellular medium (containing 1 mM ATP) and
485 then perfused with 200 nM free $[\text{Ca}^{2+}]$, as indicated. **(B)** Summary data (mean \pm
486 S.E.M.) of $[\text{Ca}^{2+}]_{\text{EL}}$ at steady-state obtained in populations of HEK293T, HeLa and
487 MDCK cells with the number of independent transfections in brackets. **(C)** Cells
488 were perfused as in (A) with an intracellular medium without ATP (-ATP) and
489 reintroduced (1 mM) when indicated. **(D)** Cells were incubated with thapsigargin (1
490 μM) during the final 10 min of reconstitution followed by the application of the
491 identical protocol described in (A). **(E)** Cells were perfused in an intracellular
492 medium containing 2,5-di-tert-butylhydroquinone (tBHQ, 10 μM) followed by
493 washout of the inhibitor. **(F)** Summary results (mean \pm S.E.M.) with statistical
494 analysis. ANOVA with Tukey's post hoc test was applied. **(G)** Cells were perfused
495 as in (A) and, once the $[\text{Ca}^{2+}]_{\text{EL}}$ steady-state was reached, different conditions
496 were tested (arrow): none (200 nM Ca^{2+} ; Control), EGTA (0.1 mM), tBHQ (10 μM),
497 EGTA+ tBHQ, or removal of ATP (-ATP). **(H)** Summary results (mean \pm S.E.M) of
498 EL- Ca^{2+} exit responses shown in (G), obtained from n (number in brackets)
499 independent experiments from at least 3 independent days. ANOVA with Tukey's
500 post hoc test was applied. * $p < 0.05$, *** $p < 0.001$, and **** $p < 0.0001$. **(I)**
501 Comparison of EL- Ca^{2+} in HEK293T cells at the steady-state using BAPTA (5 mM)
502 or EGTA buffers to clamp extraluminal $[\text{Ca}^{2+}]$ at 200 nM. Data are expressed as
503 mean \pm S.E.M. of n independent transfections in brackets. A Student's t test was
504 applied. **(J)** Comparison of passive EL Ca^{2+} -exit rate induced by tBHQ (10 μM)
505 between permeabilized and intact cells. Data are expressed as mean \pm S.E.M. of
506 n values in brackets. A Student's t test was applied. No significant differences
507 were observed.

508 **Figure 3. IP_3 releases Ca^{2+} from the endo-lysosomal Ca^{2+} store. (A)**
509 Representative response to IP_3 (2 μM , 30 s) in wt HEK293T cells expressing
510 ELGA1. **(B)** Representative EL- Ca^{2+} release (in L/Lt ratio) upon application of four
511 consecutive pulses (30s) of increasing concentrations of IP_3 (in μM). **(C)**
512 Concentration-dependent response of EL- Ca^{2+} release (expressed as % of
513 maximal response obtained with 30 μM IP_3) upon addition of increasing

514 concentrations of IP₃ (0.01, 0.1, 1 and 10 μM). Each point is the mean ± S.E.M. of
515 3-4 values obtained from independent transfections. **(D)** Representative response
516 to IP₃ (2 μM, 30 s) in IP₃R-null HEK293 (IP₃R-3KO) cell line expressing ELGA1.
517 **(E)** Representative response to IP₃ in IP₃R-3KO cells transiently expressing IP₃R1.
518 **(F)** Statistical quantification of IP₃ induced-EL-Ca²⁺ release (mean ± S.E.M.) with
519 the number of independent transfections in brackets. ANOVA with Tukey's post
520 hoc test was applied. ****p < 0.0001. **(G)** Inhibition of the IP₃ EL-Ca²⁺ release by
521 heparin (100 μg/mL) in ELGA1 expressing HEK293T cells. **(H)** Statistical
522 quantification of heparin inhibition of IP₃ response. Data are expressed as mean ±
523 S.E.M. In all bar graphs, numbers in brackets correspond to the number of
524 independent transfections from at least 2-3 experiments. A Student's *t* test was
525 applied. ****p < 0.0001.

526 **Figure 4. ELGA is functionally located to the endo-lysosome. (A, B)**
527 Representative measurements of ELGA-transiently expressing HEK293T cells **(A)**
528 or stably-expressing ELGA HeLa cells **(B)** in which NAADP (100 nM) provoked a
529 response. IP₃ (2 μM) was also added for comparison. **(C)** Representative
530 recording of HeLa cells where NAADP did not induce a response. **(D)** Statistical
531 quantifications of the NAADP responses represented as percentages of total
532 experiments performed in each cell type and quantification of the NAADP release
533 (% of EL-total Ca²⁺ content at the steady-state) in the experiments in which a
534 response was observed. **(E)** Colocalization of ELGA fluorescence with TRPML1-
535 cherry (magenta) in either fixed or live HEK293T cells expressing both proteins.
536 Scale bar in all images, 10 μm. **(F)** Quantitative colocalization analysis of confocal
537 fluorescence microscopy images were expressed as Pearson's (*P*) correlation
538 coefficient shown in (E). Data are expressed as mean ± S.E.M of 18 (Fixed) or 17
539 (Live) independent values. Each point represents an individual cell from at least 2
540 independent experiments (mean ± S.E.M). A Student's *t* test was applied.
541 **p < 0.01. **(G)** Electron microscopy images in TRPML1-Cherry expressing
542 HEK293T cells stained with antibodies against Cherry (*Upper*, single labelling;
543 scale bar, 0.3 μm) and Cherry and KDEL, as an endogenous ER marker (*Lower*,
544 double labelling; scale bar, 0.2 μm). ER, endoplasmic reticulum; E, endosome; LE,
545 late endosome. **(H)** Representative ML-SA1 (20 μM, 30 s) responses inducing EL-
546 Ca²⁺ releases (expressed as L/Lt) from HEK293T cells expressing TRPML1

547 measured with ELGA1. **(I)** Representative Ca^{2+} responses (expressed as L/Lt) to
548 application of four consecutive pulses (30s) of increasing concentrations of ML-
549 SA1. **(J)** Concentration-dependent EL- Ca^{2+} release (expressed as % of the
550 maximal response) in response to increasing concentrations of ML-SA1. Each
551 point is the mean \pm S.E.M. of 3-4 values obtained from 3 independent
552 experiments. **(K)** Effect of the TRPML1 inhibitor ML-SI1 (10 μM) on the ML-SA1
553 (20 μM) response (expressed as L/Lt) in TRPML1 transfected HEK293T cells. **(L)**
554 Effect of PI(3,5)P₂ (1 μM) on the EL- Ca^{2+} release in TRPML1 expressing
555 HEK293T cells. **(M)** Summary results and statistical quantification of EL- Ca^{2+}
556 release responses under various experimental conditions. Control (non-
557 transfected) cells and TRPML1 transfected HEK293T cells were stimulated with
558 ML-SA1 or PI(3,5)P₂. Percentage of response related to total $[\text{Ca}^{2+}]_{\text{EL}}$ at the
559 steady-state is indicated. Data are expressed as mean \pm S.E.M. and numbers in
560 brackets indicate *n* independent transfections. One-way ANOVA with a Tukey's
561 post hoc test (MLSA1 data) or a Student's *t* test (PI(3,5)P₂) were applied.
562 ****p* < 0.001 and *****p* < 0.0001. **(N)** Concentration-dependent response
563 (expressed as L/Lt) for EL- Ca^{2+} release upon increasing concentrations of
564 PI(3,5)P₂. **(O)** Summary results and statistical significance of the responses
565 determined from three independent transfections shown in (N). Results are
566 expressed as mean \pm S.E.M. An ANOVA with a Tukey's post hoc test was applied.
567 * *p* < 0.05. **(P)** TRPML3 expressing HEK293T cells were challenged with EVP-21
568 (50 μM , 30 s) or ML-SA1 (20 μM , 30 s). **(Q)** Effect of expression of TRPML1 on the
569 $[\text{Ca}^{2+}]$ at steady-state recorded from HEK293T expressing either ELGA1 (EL) or
570 ERGA1 (ER). Data are expressed as mean \pm S.E.M. In all bar graphs, numbers in
571 brackets correspond to the independent transfections. A Student's *t* test was
572 applied. *****p* < 0.0001. **(R)** Lack of correlation between resting $[\text{Ca}^{2+}]$ in the ER
573 and the EL recorded with ERGA1 or ELGA1, respectively, in six cell types: HEK,
574 TRPML1-expressing HEK, 3KO HEK, HeLa, CHO cells and cultured murine
575 cortical astrocytes. Data are expressed as mean \pm S.E.M. ER- Ca^{2+} in astrocytes
576 data were taken from (Rodríguez-Prados et al., 2020). **(S)** Representative ML-SA1
577 (20 μM) and IP₃ (2 μM) responses of ER- Ca^{2+} dynamics in HEK293T cells
578 expressing TRPML1, measured with ERGA1. **(T)** Selected experiment where
579 EGTA (0.5 mM) was replaced by BAPTA (5 mM) buffer and the ML-SA-1 effect
580 was completely blocked but not the effect provoked by IP₃. **(U)** Effect of BAPTA

581 on the ML-SA1 and IP₃ responses in the EL of HEK293T cells expressing
582 TRPML1 measured with ELGA1. **(V)** Summary results and statistical quantification
583 of the results shown in **(S-U)**. Data are expressed as mean ± S.E.M. Numbers in
584 brackets indicate total *n* of independent transfections. Student's *t* test was applied,
585 * *p* < 0.05.

586 **Figure 5. ELGA is physically located to the endo-lysosome. (A)** Colocalization
587 of endogenous IP₃R1 with various endo-lysosome markers in EGFP-IP₃R1 HeLa
588 cells using STED microscopy. Cells were transiently transfected with cherry-
589 TRPML1 **(a, b)** or mRFP-TPC2 **(c,d)**. EGFP-IP₃R1 and LAMP2 were detected
590 using specific antibodies against EGFP and LAMP2 **(e,f)**. **(B)** Association (arrows)
591 of endogenous IP₃R3 with LAMP1 detected with specific antibodies anti-IP₃R3 and
592 anti-LAMP1 in fixed wild type HEK293 cells using STED Super-resolution
593 microscopy. **(C)** Colocalization (arrows) of endo-lysosomes stained with
594 LysoView650 (pink) and endogenous IP₃R1-EGFP in live HeLa cells using live cell
595 STED microscopy. **(D)** Colocalization (arrows) of endo-lysosomes stained with
596 lysotracker red (pink) and endogenous IP₃R1-EGFP in HeLa cells using TIRFM.
597 **(E)** Association (arrows) of endogenous IP₃R1-EGFP with ELSA (Endo-Lysosome
598 Scarlet Aequorin) in EGFP-IP₃R1 HeLa cells expressing ELSA.

599 **Figure 6. Physiological endo-lysosomal Ca²⁺ release. (A)** Representative EL-
600 Ca²⁺ responses (in L/Lt) to agonists (ML-SA1, 20 μM; ATP, 100 μM; Carbachol,
601 (CCh), 100 μM) in intact HEK293T cells expressing ELGA1. **(B)** Similar to (A), in
602 transiently expressing TRPML1 HEK293T cells. **(C)** Protocol similar to (A) applied
603 in MDCK cells. **(D)** Protocol similar to (A) applied in astrocytes. **(E)** Summary
604 results of EL-Ca²⁺ release induced by ML-SA1 and ATP in different cell types or
605 conditions. Data are expressed as mean ± S.E.M. and numbers in brackets
606 correspond to the total number of independent transfections. Responses are in
607 percentages related to total [Ca²⁺]_{EL} at the steady-state. **(F)** A proposed model of
608 Ca²⁺ dynamics in the endo-lysosome (see text for explanation).

609 SUPPLEMENTARY FIGURE LEGENDS

610 **Fig. S1.**

611 **Properties of GA and GA1 bioluminescent Ca²⁺ sensors and effect of acidic**
612 **pH on luminescence emission. (A)** Ca²⁺ calibration of GA and GA1. Marked

613 region is the expected range of $[Ca^{2+}]$ in the EL. **(B-D)** *E.coli* recombinant GA1
614 reconstituted with either native- **(B)** or *n*-coelenterazine (CTZ) **(C)**, and wt-
615 Aequorin (AEQ) reconstituted with *n*-coelenterazine **(D)** for 20 min at the indicated
616 pHs, and then subjected to luminescence emission assay triggered with 10 mM
617 $CaCl_2$ (arrow) and measured at the same pH. Buffers used were: acetate for range
618 4.5-5.5 pH; Na-MOPS for 6 and 6.5 pH; and Na-Hepes for 7.2 pH. Each trace is
619 the value normalized with respect to its background emission before addition of
620 calcium and corresponds to the average of 3-4 independent experiments. **(E, F)**
621 Comparison of luminescence emission and consumption (in % of the total) in a
622 representative experiment in transiently transfected HeLa cells with ELGA **(E)** or
623 ELGA1 **(F)**. Note the stability of the ELGA1 signal at the steady-state (less than
624 5% consumption at min 8) in comparison with the ELGA signal that quickly
625 declines due to the rapid consumption (~50% at the same timepoint).

626 **Fig. S2.**

627 **Properties of the ER marker er-Ruby-GCaMP250, ELGA localization to the**
628 **endo-lysosome, and effect of vacuolin on ELGA vesicles. (A)** Transiently
629 transfected HeLa cells expressing er-Ruby-GCaMP250 (Farrell et al., 2024)
630 display red fluorescence (magenta, 568 channel) and not green fluorescence (488
631 channel). The pattern of cell expression of er-Ruby-GCaMP250 in the ER
632 colocalized with that of calreticulin, an ER resident protein, detected with an anti-
633 calreticulin antibody and revealed in green. Nuclei (in merge) were stained with
634 DAPI. Scale bar, 5 μm . **(B, C)** Detail of one Z- plane (1 μm) from super-resolution
635 images taken of HEK293T cells co-expressing: ELGA (green) with an ER marker
636 (Ruby-GCaMP250; magenta) **(B)**, or ELGA (green) with TRPML1-Cherry
637 (magenta; **C**). Scale bars (B, C): 5 μm ; insets, 1 μm . **(D)** Detail of one Z plane of a
638 confocal microscopy image of HeLa cells stably expressing ELGA treated
639 overnight with vacuolin (10 μM) or vehicle DMSO (Control). Scale bar, 5 μm .

640 **Fig. S3.**

641 **EL- Ca^{2+} uptake and EL- Ca^{2+} release induced by IP_3 in various cell types. (A)**
642 Treatment of ELGA1-expressing HEK293 cells with Bafilomycin A1 does not
643 deplete the target store of Ca^{2+} and produced no increase in the amount of
644 luminescence (in cps). Cells were incubated with Bafilomycin A1 (1 μM) for 10 min

645 in EGTA (0.5 mM) prior to be reconstituted with coelenterazine n containing
646 Bafilomycin A for 1-2h. Cells were permeabilized with digitonin (20 μ M) and then
647 perfused with 200 nM Ca^{2+} . The total content of unconsumed aequorin was
648 released with digitonin (100 μ M) in the presence of 10 mM Ca^{2+} . The total amount
649 of counts was one order less than that obtained in experiments using inhibitors of
650 SERCA pump (B,C), indicating that the aequorin into the EL has been consumed
651 due to the high Ca^{2+} content during the reconstitution with coelenterazine n.
652 Representative responses of EL- Ca^{2+} uptake **(B)** and IP_3 -induced EL- Ca^{2+} release
653 **(C)** in various cell types: HeLa, CHO, MDCK and cortical astrocytes. All the cells
654 transiently expressed ELGA1. Concentration of IP_3 used was 2 μ M. For further
655 details, refer to Figure 2.

656 **Fig. S4.**

657 **Bafilomycin A1 does neither affect EL- Ca^{2+} uptake nor EL- Ca^{2+} release**
658 **induced by NAADP or IP_3 .** **(A)** ELGA transiently expressing HeLa cells were
659 preincubated with Bafilomycin A1 (1 μ M, blue trace) or DMSO (red trace) for 1h.
660 For further experimental details refer to Figure 2. **(B)** Acute application of
661 Bafilomycin A1 (1 μ M, 120s). Traces (A,B) are the mean \pm S.E.M. of 6
662 experiments from, at least, 2 independent days. **(C)** Representative
663 measurements in HeLa cells stably-expressing ELGA incubated for 3h with
664 Bafilomycin A1 (1 μ M; Baf A1). Cells were stimulated with NAADP (100 nM) or IP_3
665 (2 μ M). **(D)** Summary responses (mean \pm S.E.M, n=6) shown in (C) of 2
666 independent days. Each point represents an independent well treated with vehicle
667 (0.5% DMSO (v/v); control) or Bafilomycin A1. A Student's *t* test was applied. No
668 significant differences were found.

669 **Fig. S5.**

670 **IP_3R is neither essential for EL- Ca^{2+} refilling nor for TRPML1 activation, and**
671 **EL- Ca^{2+} -release with ML-SA1 through activation of TRMPL1 is blocked by**
672 **specific inhibitors.** Comparison of resting $[\text{Ca}^{2+}]_{\text{EL}}$ **(A)** and EL-refilling Ca^{2+} rate
673 **(B)** between control and IP_3R -3KO cells. Values are expressed as mean \pm
674 S.E.M. Numbers in brackets indicate the number of independent transfections. A
675 Student's *t* test was applied. No significant differences were observed. **(C)** ELGA
676 expressing HeLa cells were challenged with ML-SA1 (20 μ M, 30 s). **(C-E)** Similar

677 to protocol in (A), but in transiently expressing-TRPML1 HeLa cells. The second
678 application of ML-SA1 was performed in the presence of ML-SI1 (10 μ M) (D) or
679 ML-SI3 (10 μ M) (E). (F) Comparison between the ML-SA1 and the IP₃ responses.
680 Heparin (100 μ g/mL) completely inhibited the IP₃ response leaving intact the
681 response induced by ML-SA1. wt HEK293T cells (G) or IP₃R-3KO HEK cells (H)
682 transiently expressing-TRPML1 and ELGA1 were challenged with ML-SA1 (20 μ M,
683 30 s) and IP₃ (2 μ M). (I) Summary data of ML-SA1 response or EL-Ca²⁺ content in
684 pooled experiments. *n* of independent experiments is shown in brackets. Values
685 are expressed as mean \pm S.E.M. of *n* independent experiments. A Student's *t* test
686 was applied. No significant differences are found both in the ML-SA1 response or
687 in the amount of stored Ca²⁺ in the EL at the steady-state.

688 **Fig. S6.**

689 **BAPTA treatment does not modify IP₃ responses, and EVP-21 is a specific**
690 **activator of TRPML3.** (A) Representative measurements of HEK293T cells
691 transiently expressing ELGA1 where free [Ca²⁺] of 200 nM was achieved by using
692 the buffer BAPTA (5 mM) instead of EGTA (0.5 mM). Cells were stimulated with
693 IP₃ (2 μ M). (B) Comparison of responses using BAPTA or EGTA buffers on EL
694 Ca²⁺ steady-state in naive cells. (C) Comparison of IP₃-induced Ca²⁺ release of
695 EL-total Ca²⁺ in naive cells. Data are expressed as mean \pm S.E.M of 18 (EGTA) or
696 4 (BAPTA) independent values. (D) Comparison of IP₃-induced Ca²⁺ release of
697 EL-total Ca²⁺ in TRPML-1 expressing cells. Data are expressed as mean \pm S.E.M
698 of 19 (EGTA) or 8 (BAPTA) independent values. A Student's *t* test was applied.
699 No significant differences were observed. (E, F) HEK293T cells transiently
700 expressing TRPML1 (E) or TRPML3 (F), together with ELGA1, were challenged
701 with EVP-21 (50 μ M, 30 s) or ML-SA1 (20 μ M, 30 s). (G) Summary data pooled
702 from at least 3 independent experiments. Data are expressed as mean \pm S.E.M.

703 **Fig. S7.**

704 **TRPML1 localizes to the endo-lysosomes, but not to the ER.** (A) A super-
705 resolution image of two individual endo-lysosomes in one Z-plane showing
706 colocalization of ELGA and TRPML1. Quantification data are shown in **Table S2**.
707 Scale bar, 5 μ m. (B, C) Two representative electron microscopy images of
708 TRPML1-Cherry expressing HEK293T cells double-stained with antibodies against

709 Cherry (coupled to 15 nm gold particles) and endogenous KDEL (coupled to 10
710 nm gold particles), as an endogenous ER marker. ER, endoplasmic reticulum; EL,
711 endo-lysosome. Scale bar, 0.25 μm .

712

713 **Fig. S8.**

714 **SERCA partial colocalization with endo-lysosome marker and properties of**
715 **the red EL-Ca²⁺ indicator ELSA. (A)** Detail of one Z plane of a super-resolution
716 image of HEK293T cells expressing EGFP-SERCA2b (green) labelled for LAMP2
717 (magenta). Arrows indicate puncta of colocalization. Quantification data are shown
718 in **Table S2**. Scale bar, 5 μm . **(B)**. Detail of one Z plane from a super-resolution
719 microscopy image shown in Fig. 5E of HEK293T cells transiently expressing ELSA
720 (Endo-Lysosome Scarlet-Aequorin). Scale bar, 5 μm . **(C)**. Representative
721 response to IP₃ (2 μM) in HEK293T cells expressing ELSA.

722

723 **Video 1.**

724 **Pattern of expression of ELGA in MDCK cells**

725 Fluorescence confocal microscopy images, each corresponding to 0.38 μm , of a fixed
726 MDCK cell transiently expressing the endo-lysosomal Ca²⁺ indicator ELGA. The observed
727 green fluorescence puncta show that ELGA localizes to a subset of endo-lysosomes. Fig.
728 2C shows a still image of one equatorial frame of this video.

729

730 **METHODS**

731 **Gene construction**

732 *H. sapiens* VAMP7 cDNA was amplified by PCR using specific primers (#324;
733 forward: 5'-CCAaagcttGCCACCATGGCGATTCTTTTT-3'; #325; reverse: 5'-
734 ATaagcttTTTCTTCACACAGCTTGGCCATG-3'; *HindIII* sites are in lowercase).
735 This fragment was digested with *HindIII* and inserted upstream of the *HindIII*
736 fragment encoding the GA or the GA1 cDNAs, in the pHSV plasmid leading to
737 pHSV-ELGA or pHSV-ELGA1 plasmids, respectively. These plasmids are
738 deposited to Addgene with No. #246796 and #246926, respectively. The GA gene
739 is a fusion of EGFP and aequorin (Manjarres et al., 2008) containing the D119A
740 mutation (Kendall et al., 1992). The GA1 (previously described as GAP1) gene is a
741 fusion of GFP (C3) and aequorin containing the mutations D117A, D119A and
742 D163A (Rodriguez-Garcia et al., 2014). For expression in bacteria, GA or GA1
743 cDNAs were cloned into the pET28a vector. For measurements of ER-Ca²⁺, the
744 pHSV-ERGA1 (previously described as erGAP1) was used (Rodriguez-Prados et
745 al., 2015). To generate the plasmid pHSV-ELSA we originally PCR-amplified the
746 Scarlet gene from the pRB-Scarlet plasmid using the specific primers (#498;
747 forward: 5'TTgctagcGTGAGCAAGGGCGAG-3'; and #499, reverse: 5'-
748 CGgctagcCTTGTACAGCTCGTCCA-3', *NheI* sites are in lowercase. This 696pb-
749 PCR fragment was digested with *NheI* and inserted between VAMP7 and
750 wtAequorin in the pHSV-VAMP7-wtAequorin plasmid, by ligating the Scarlet
751 fragment with the *NheI*-digested plasmid. The resulting plasmid was checked by
752 sequencing. The EGFP-Serca 2b plasmid was generated previously (Manjarres et
753 al., 2010).

754 **Virus production**

755 pHSV-ELGA or pHSV-ELGA1 were packaged into HSV-1 amplicon particles using
756 a deletion mutant packaging system. Briefly, these plasmids were transfected into
757 2-2 cells (Smith et al., 1992) and then, infected with a defective 5dl 1.2 helper virus
758 (McCarthy et al., 1989). Titration was performed as previously described (Alonso
759 et al., 1996; Lim et al., 1996).

760 **Bacterial expression of GA and GA1 proteins**

761 GA or GA1 cloned in pET28a were transformed in *E. coli* BL21 (Stratagene).
762 Bacteria were grown at 37° C to A₆₀₀ >0.6 in LB containing 40 mg/L kanamycin
763 and induced with 0.05 mM isopropyl β-D-thiogalactoside (IPTG) for 5h at 30°.
764 Cells were then pelleted by centrifugation at 6000 g for 30 min and sonicated in a
765 buffer containing (in mM): NaCl, 50; DTT, 0.5; Tris-HCl 20, pH 7.5; and Roche
766 protein inhibitors. The bacterial lysate was centrifuged at 30,000 g for 10 min.
767 Protein was purified by using a HisPur Ni-NTA resin (ThermoFisher, 88222).
768 Protein quantification was performed by Bradford (range 20-60 µg/µL).

769 **Bioluminescence activity at various pHs**

770 Measurements were performed in the Tecan Genios Pro 96-well plate reader.
771 Recombinant *E.coli* GA or GA1 protein was reconstituted with coelenterazine *n* (1
772 µM) for 20 min and then 5-10 µL were aliquoted into each well to a final volume of
773 100 µL with a buffer containing (in mM): KCl, 140; MgCl₂, 1; MOPS/Tris, 20, pH
774 7.2. The effects of pH were monitored using different buffers for each pH range:
775 acetate for pH in the range 4.5-5.5; MOPS/Na for pH range 6-6.5; and Hepes/Na
776 for pH 7.2. Maximal luminescence was acquired by injecting 10-25 µL of saturating
777 (50 mM) Ca²⁺. Calibrations were performed in Ca²⁺-free medium (0.1 mM EGTA
778 added), or in the same solutions containing increasing Ca²⁺ concentrations
779 between 50 µM and 50 mM. This Ca²⁺solution (10 µL) was injected with a first
780 injector, read for 15 seconds and then a saturating Ca²⁺ solution (10 mM) was
781 injected with a second injector.

782 **Cell culture and gene expression**

783 HeLa (CCL-2), HEK 293-T (CLR-1573), CHO- K1 (CCL-61) or MDCK cells (CCL-
784 34), were all purchased from ATCC. EGFP-IP₃R1 HeLa cells were earlier
785 described (Thillaiappan et al., 2017). All cells were maintained in Dulbecco's
786 Modified Eagle Medium (DMEM, Invitrogen) supplemented with 10% fetal bovine
787 serum (FBS, Sigma), 2 mM L-glutamine, 100 µg/ml streptomycin and 100 U/ml
788 penicillin. IP₃R-null HEK293 (HEK-3KO) cells (Alzayady et al., 2016) were
789 maintained in DMEM/F-12 with GlutaMAX (ThermoFisher) supplemented with
790 10%, FBS. Periodic PCR screening confirmed that all cells were free of
791 mycoplasma infection.

792 Mouse cortical astrocytes were isolated using the protocol described previously
793 (Rodríguez-Prados et al., 2020) with the approval of the Institutional Animal Care
794 and Use Committee at the University of Valladolid (ethics approval reference
795 number: 10207729). Briefly, cortices were dissected from three P2-3 C57BL/6J Crl
796 (Charles Rivers) mice in cold HBSS and digested with 0.5 mg/mL papain and 0.04
797 mg/mL DNase dissolved in a Ca²⁺- and Mg-free HBSS with 10 mM glucose and
798 0.1% bovine serum albumin (BSA) at 37°C for 20 min. Cells were resuspended
799 with Minimal Essential Medium (MEM) supplemented with 2 mM glutamax, 27 mM
800 glucose, 100 U/mL penicillin, 100 µg/mL streptomycin and 10% (v/v) horse serum,
801 and plated on a poly-L-lysine coated 75 cm² flask. After 2 and 7 days, flasks were
802 slapped to remove neurons and other loosely attached cells such as microglia and
803 oligodendrocytes. After one week, cells were trypsinized and seeded in the same
804 medium onto poly-L-lysine coated 12 mm-diameter glass coverslips at a density of
805 2.5 x 10⁴ cells/coverslip. The cultures were used within 1-2 weeks.

806 The EGFP-Serca 2b plasmid was generated previously (Manjarres et al., 2010).

807 Cells were transiently transfected with 0.2 µg (HEK293T) or 0.2-0.5 µg (HeLa)
808 pHSV-ELGA, pHSV-ELGA1 or pHSV-ELSA using Lipofectamine 2000 (Invitrogen),
809 according to the manufacturer's instructions. In some experiments, this plasmid
810 was cotransfected with other plasmids encoding: mRFP-TPC2 ((Brailoiu et al.,
811 2009); 0.1 µg); EGFP-trpML1 (0.02 µg); trpML1-mCherry (0.05 µg; Addgene
812 #135189); trpML3-YFP ((Grimm et al., 2010); 0.03 µg); er-Ruby-GCaMP210
813 ((Farrell et al., 2024); 0.5 µg); or IP₃R1 (0.02 µg). Stably transfected HeLa clones
814 expressing ELGA1 were generated by cotransfection of pHSV-ELGA1 and
815 pcDNA3 (carrying the *neomycin* gene). GFP positive cells were enriched by
816 sorting in a FACS Aria II followed by antibiotic selection with 800 µg/mL G418 and
817 single cell cloning was performed by limited dilution. ELGA1-HeLa clones (No. 3
818 and 6) were maintained with 200 µg/mL G418.

819 ELGAs or ERGA expression in mouse cortical astrocyte cultures was achieved by
820 infection with herpes HSV-ELGA, HSV-ELGA1 or HSV-ERGA1 (previously named
821 erGAP1) amplicons at a multiplicity of infection ranging between 0.01 and 0.1, one
822 day before use.

823 **Ca²⁺ bioluminescence measurements**

824 Cells expressing ELGA1 (or ELGA in some experiments) were seeded on 4-well
825 plates at a density of 8×10^4 (HeLa, CHO, or MDCK cells) or 2×10^5 (HEK-293T
826 and HEK-3KO cells). Cells were Ca^{2+} depleted by incubation with the reversible
827 sarco-endoplasmic reticulum Ca^{2+} -ATPase (SERCA) inhibitor 2,5-di-tert-
828 butylhydroquinone (TBH; 10 μM) in the extracellular buffer (145 mM NaCl; 5 mM
829 KCl; 1 mM MgCl_2 ; 10 mM glucose; 10 mM Na-HEPES, pH 7.4) supplemented with
830 0.5 mM EGTA for 10 min at 22°C. Apo-aequorin was then reconstituted by
831 incubation with 1 μM *n* coelenterazine in the same medium during 1h prior to
832 measurements. Cells were then placed in the luminometer (Cairn Research, UK).
833 Light acquisition was recorded each second as cps.

834 Intact cells were perfused (5 mL/min) with the extracellular buffer containing 1 mM
835 CaCl_2 plus additions as stated. In the experiments with permeabilized cells,
836 perfusion was performed with an intracellular-like (IL) medium with the following
837 composition (in mM): KCl, 140; KH_2PO_4 , 1; MgCl_2 1; Mg-ATP, 1; sodium
838 succinate, 2; sodium-pyruvate, 1; Na-HEPES, 20, pH 7.2. Cells were
839 permeabilized by perfusion of digitonin (50 μM) in the IL medium containing 0.5
840 mM EGTA during 1 min. The digitonin was washed out and cells were then
841 switched to IL medium containing 200 nM Ca^{2+} made by blending titrated solutions
842 of EGTA (0.5 mM) and EGTA- Ca^{2+} in the required amounts, calculated using the
843 program MaxChelator (Patton et al., 2004). In some experiments, 0.5 mM BAPTA
844 replaced EGTA in IL medium to obtain 200 nM free Ca^{2+} . If not stated otherwise,
845 all stimuli or drugs were dissolved and applied in the IL-buffer containing 200 nM
846 Ca^{2+} during 30s, as indicated in the graphs. At the end of each run, cells were
847 lysed with 100 μM digitonin in a 10 mM CaCl_2 solution to release all the remaining
848 aequorin luminescence. The EL- Ca^{2+} was expressed as luminescence at a certain
849 time point (L) divided by total luminescence till that moment (L/Lt). All
850 measurements were performed at 22°C. Calibration curve allowed to transform
851 L/Lt into $[\text{Ca}^{2+}]$ (μM) (Rodriguez-Prados et al., 2015).

852 **Immunofluorescence**

853 $2-5 \times 10^4$ HEK cells were seeded onto 12 mm-glass coverslips and fixed, either
854 with cold 100% methanol or with 4% PFA in PBS for 20 min, followed by
855 incubation with 10% goat serum, 0.2% saponin (or 1% goat serum with 0.1%

856 Tween-20 in some experiments) in PBS for 20 min at 22 °C. The incubation with
857 the primary antibody was performed overnight at 4°C. The following primary
858 antibodies were used: anti-IP3R1 (1:1000; home-made (Arige et al., 2022)); anti-
859 IP₃R3 (1:1000; BD biosciences; CAT. 610312); anti-LAMP1 (1:1000; Cell
860 Signaling; CAT. C54H11); anti-LAMP2 (1:100; DSHB / University of Iowa; CAT.
861 H4B4); anti-EEA1 (1:200; BD Transduction Laboratories; CAT. 610456); anti-
862 TOM20 (1:100; Santa Cruz; CAT. sc-17764); and, anti-GFP (1:500; Invitrogen;
863 CAT. CAB4211). The secondary antibodies (anti-mouse Alexa Fluor 568-
864 conjugated antibodies; CAT. A-11031) were incubated for 1h at 22 °C. Cells were
865 mounted with Vectashield containing 4',6-diamidino-2-phenylindole (DAPI;
866 VECTOR Laboratories; CAT. H-1200) to stain nuclei.

867 **Confocal microscopy**

868 Intact or fixed cells were imaged at 22 °C under a 63X Plan-Apochromat (NA 1.4)
869 oil immersion objective using a confocal microscope (SP5 Leica) equipped with a
870 white laser. Images were analyzed with ImageJ software using the JACoP plugin
871 (Bolte and Cordelières, 2006). Negative controls were obtained by rotating one of
872 the two images by 180°.

873 **STED microscopy**

874 3D STED microscopy was performed at 22 °C using a Leica SP8-STED
875 microscope equipped with an HC PL APO CS2 x100/1.4NA oil immersion
876 objective. Fluorescence depletion was made by a white laser and using a LAS-X
877 deconvolution software. Some experiments were performed with an Abberior
878 Instruments Expert Line STED microscope equipped with an Olympus UPLSAPO
879 ×100/1.4NA oil immersion objective. Sequential confocal and STED images were
880 obtained following excitation of Alexa Fluor 594 and STAR RED by 594 and 640
881 nm lasers, respectively. Both fluorophores were depleted in three dimensions with
882 a 775 nm pulsed STED laser. Z-stacks were obtained by collecting images at 50
883 nm intervals using the 3D STED mode. Rescue STED was employed to minimize
884 the light dosage. Images were analyzed with ImageJ software using the JACoP
885 plugin.

886 **Electron Microscopy**

887 Tokuyasu sample preparation was done as described (Slot and Geuze, 2007).
888 HeLa cells were fixed overnight at 4°C with 0.1 M PHEM buffer, 4% (w/v)
889 paraformaldehyde. Cells were scraped and embedded in 12% (w/v) gelatin in 0.1
890 M PHEM buffer at 37°C, which was allowed to set at 4°C before being cut into
891 small cubes measuring approximately 0.5 mm on each edge. The gelatin
892 embedded cells were infiltrated with 2.3 M sucrose in 0.1 M PHEM buffer at 4°C
893 overnight on a rocker. The sucrose infiltrated gelatin blocks were mounted on
894 cryo-pins, and then frozen in liquid nitrogen for cryo-ultramicrotomy. Frozen
895 samples were trimmed at -100°C and sectioned at -120°C using a Cryo-EM UC7
896 ultramicrotome (Leica) equipped with a 45° diamond cryo-trimming knife (Diatome)
897 and a 35° diamond cryo-immuno knife (Diatome). Cryo-sections were retrieved by
898 pick-up loop with a droplet of phosphate buffered 1% (w/v) methyl cellulose and
899 1.15 M sucrose, then deposited on carbon-coated formvar grids for
900 immunolabelling. The grids were prepared for immunolabelling by melting up-side-
901 down on PHEM at 37°C, then rinsing the grids on droplets of 0.02 M glycine in
902 PHEM (4x2 min). The grids were blocked with 1% (w/v) bovine serum albumin
903 (BSA) in PHEM (5 min), incubated with rabbit anti RFP (1:300, Rockland 600-401-
904 379) in 1% (w/v) BSA in PHEM (25°C; 30 min.). Then rinsed with 0.1% (w/v) BSA in
905 PHEM (5x2 min). The grids were then incubated with Protein-A conjugated 10 nm
906 gold particles diluted (1:25, Cell Biology UMC-Utrecht) in 1% (w/v) BSA in PHEM
907 (22 °C; 20 min), rinsed with PHEM (5x2 min). After stabilization of the reaction by
908 1% glutaraldehyde (w/v) in PHEM for 5 min, grids were rinsed in distilled water
909 (8x2 min). Finally, the grids were stained with 2% (w/v) uranylacetate (pH 7;
910 room temperature; 5 min) and 0.4% (w/v) uranyl acetate in 1.8% (w/v) aqueous
911 methyl cellulose (pH 4; 4°C; 5 min) and dried in a thin film of the final stain in the
912 centre of a wire loop. EM imaging was done on a Jeol1400-Flash TEM at 120kV.
913 In case of double labeling the procedure was performed as described above. The
914 order of antibodies was as follows: firstly, mouse anti KDEL 10C3 (1:1000, Sigma-
915 Aldrich 420400) was followed by a bridging step of Rabbit anti Mouse IgG (1:1000,
916 Rockland 610-4120) and Protein-A conjugated 10 nm gold particles diluted (1:25,
917 Cell Biology UMC-Utrecht). Stabilization of the reaction by 1% glutaraldehyde
918 (w/v) in PHEM for 5 min. Secondly, rabbit anti RFP (1:300, Rockland 600-401-379)
919 was followed by Protein-A conjugated 15 nm gold particles diluted (1:25, Cell

920 Biology UMC-Utrecht). Again, the reaction was stabilized by 1% glutaraldehyde
921 (w/v) in PHEM for 5 min prior to staining.

922 **TIRFM**

923 Images were acquired using an Olympus IX81 inverted Total Internal Reflection
924 Fluorescence Microscopy (TIRFM) equipped with oil-immersion PLAPO OTIRFM
925 60x objective lens/1.45 numerical aperture. Olympus CellSens Dimensions 2.3
926 (Build 189987) software was used for imaging. The cells were illuminated using
927 488 or 568 nm laser and the emitted fluorescence was collected through a band-
928 pass filter by a Hamamatsu ORCA-Fusion CMOS camera. The angle of the
929 excitation beam was adjusted to achieve TIRF with a penetration depth of ~140
930 nm.

931 **Statistical analysis**

932 Results are expressed as mean \pm S.E.M., as indicated. Data were analyzed with
933 the GraphPad Prism 9 software (San Diego, CA, USA). After confirming the
934 normal distribution of data by the Shapiro-Wilk test, statistical significance between
935 two groups was analyzed by the unpaired two-tailed Student's *t* test, whereas
936 more than two groups were compared using one-way analysis of variance
937 (ANOVA) and Tukey post-test analysis. Differences were considered statistically
938 significant when probability (*p*) values were less or equal than 0.05 (*), 0.01 (**),
939 0.001 (***) or 0.0001(****). Sample sizes (*n*) refer to cell wells independently
940 transfected from, at least, 3 different days. Individual traces show representative
941 experiments.

942 **Online supplemental material**

943 **Fig. S1** shows the properties of GA and GA1 bioluminescent Ca²⁺ sensors and the
944 effect of acidic pH on luminescence emission. **Video 1** shows a representative
945 example of the localization of ELGA to punctate structures compatible with endo-
946 lysosome in MDCK cells. **Fig. S2** shows that er-Ruby-GCaMP250 is a red
947 fluorescent ER marker, that ELGA indicator is localized to the endo-lysosome, but
948 not to the ER, and that vacuolin treatment improves the visualization of the
949 localization of ELGA within the EL vesicles. **Table S1** shows the colocalization of
950 ELGA with organelle markers. **Fig. S3** shows that Bafilomycin A1 does not empty

951 of Ca²⁺ the EL target store and examples of EL-Ca²⁺ uptake and EL-Ca²⁺ release
952 induced by IP₃ in various cell types. **Fig. S4** shows that Bafilomycin A1 does
953 neither affect EL-Ca²⁺ uptake nor EL-Ca²⁺ release induced by NAADP or IP₃. **Fig.**
954 **S5** shows that IP₃R is neither essential for EL-Ca²⁺ refilling nor for TRPML1
955 activation and that EL-Ca²⁺-release with MLSA1 through activation of TRMPL1 is
956 blocked by specific inhibitors. **Fig. S6** shows that BAPTA treatment does not
957 modify IP₃ responses and that EVP-21 is a specific activator of TRPML3. **Table**
958 **S2** shows the super-resolution analysis of colocalization. **Fig. S7** shows
959 representative immunofluorescence and electron microscope images where
960 TRPML1 localizes to the endo-lysosomes, but not to the ER. **Fig. S8** shows a
961 representative example of an immunofluorescence image of SERCA partial
962 colocalization with an endo-lysosome marker, and that ELSA is a functional red
963 EL-Ca²⁺ indicator. **Video 1** shows pattern of expression of ELGA in MDCK cells.

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972 **Credit authorship contribution statement**

973 Belen Calvo: data curation, formal analysis, investigation, methodology, validation,
974 visualization, and writing—original draft, review, and editing. Patricia Torres- Vidal:
975 conceptualization, formal analysis, investigation, methodology, validation,
976 visualization, and writing—review and editing. Alba Delrio-Lorenzo: investigation.
977 Carla Rodriguez: investigation, resources, validation, and visualization. Francisco J.
978 Aulestia: conceptualization, formal analysis, investigation, methodology, validation,
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980 analysis, investigation, supervision, validation, and writing—review and editing.
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982 Marco Keller: resources. Christian Grimm: methodology and resources. Viola

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984 writing—review and editing. David I. Yule: formal analysis, funding acquisition,
985 investigation, project administration, and resources. Javier Garcia-Sancho:
986 conceptualization and funding acquisition. Sandip Patel: conceptualization,
987 methodology, resources, visualization, and writing—original draft, review, and
988 editing. M. Teresa Alonso: conceptualization, data curation, formal analysis, funding
989 acquisition, investigation, methodology, project administration, supervision,
990 validation, visualization, and writing—original draft, review, and editing.

991 **Declaration of Competing interest**

992 The authors declare no competing financial interests.

993 **Data availability**

994 All data used in this study are available upon request.

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Fig. S7.

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Fig. S8.